

THE EMERGENCE OF INFORMATION SECURITY IN SLOVAKIAN AND HUNGARIAN CURRICULA

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Abstract

Teaching information security in elementary and high school education is becoming increasingly important in today's digital society. Young people take advantage of the Internet almost daily and participate in online activities, so data handling, protection, and security have become extremely important issues. Teaching information security at the related school levels is key in informing students of basic methods and principles to protect their personal data in digital space. To understand how information security education is currently widespread in the two Central European countries Slovakia and Hungary, it's important to know how many lessons per week the Information Technology (IT) is taught in these countries and what emphasis is placed on information security in the National Core Curriculum (NCC). My research compares information security education in these two countries based on the education curriculum.

Keywords

Curriculum, Slovakia, Hungary, education, information security

1 Introduction

Information security education is very important in the digital world so that children can know the basics of privacy and online safety. Information security education in schools helps students learn how to protect their personal and sensitive data online. It's important to prepare students for the challenges and dangers of the digital world and provide knowledge that helps them operate safely in online space.

The aim of the work is to explore what emphasis is placed in the National Core Curriculum (NCC) for information security in Slovakia and Hungary. Furthermore, it is needed to explore which country places a bigger emphasis on information security education.

2 IT lessons in Slovakia and Hungary

Slovakia has two Information Technology (IT) lessons during the four years of lower primary education. This is also the case in Hungary.

In Slovakia, upper primary education has four Information Technology (IT) lessons for five years. The same is true in Hungary; however, there are only four classes in Hungarian upper primary education.

Figure 1. illustrates that grammar school classes have three Information Technology (IT) lessons in Slovakia during the whole education; however, in Hungary it is five.

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Fig. 1: IT lessons in Slovakia (Domov, 2023) and Hungary (Magyar, 2023)

Source: Author

3 Education system in Slovakia

In Slovakia, the National Core Curriculum is a directive that defines the general goals of education and the key skills that education should focus on. The national curriculum determines what should be acquired by the students in each year. This is the basis for developing the school curriculum. The state education program is issued and published by the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic for all educational levels (Štátny, 2023).

3.1 School Curriculum in Slovakia

Considering the regulations, the school can decide when the individual teaching materials will be included in the given level. At each level (lower elementary school, upper elementary school, grammar school), the number of mandatory hours is defined. However, schools are given a certain level of freedom regarding which subjects and classes they want to teach in an increased number of hours (Rámcové, 2023).

3.2 The emergence of information security in the IT core curriculum in Slovakia

In Slovakia, performance and content standards are linked with each topic's IT core curriculum.

In lower primary classes, the following items are written in performance standards:

- to have a dialogue with students about the dangers of the Internet,
- students can apply rules to protect e-mail accounts against unauthorised use.

In the content standard, the following item is written:

- safe attitude in online space (INFORMATIKA, 2023).

The topic of security and risk in the Information Technology core curriculum defines that by the end of the 6th grade, students should be able to:

- discuss the dangers of the Internet,

- apply the rules for the protection of data, including e-mail, against unauthorised use,
- talk about cybercrime,
- discuss the authenticity of information found on the web.

The content standard includes the following:

- virus as malicious software,
- the authenticity of the information obtained, risks on the Internet and social network risks,
- distribution of computer viruses and spam,
- safe and ethical behaviour on the Internet, activities of hackers.

At the end of the upper primary classes, the student's performance standard according to the IT core curriculum:

- how to talk about the risks of the Internet,
- ability to evaluate which information must be protected from abuse,
- apply the rules about email access and rules against unauthorised use of the community and computer,
- be able to assess the dangers of using malicious software,
- be able to talk about computer crime,
- be able to discuss the reliability of information found on the World Wide Web
- be able to talk about the risks of criminal and illegal content.

Content standard:

- the virus as malware,
- spam as junk mail,
- antivirus as a means of protection against viruses,
- the quality of passwords as a security mechanism,
- the reliability of the information obtained,
- risks on the Internet and social networks.
- distribution of computer viruses and spam,
- safe and ethical behaviour on the Internet,
- and activity of hackers (Nižšie, 2023).

Security and risk also appear in the Information Technology lessons in the curriculum of grammar school education. In the performance standard, the student can:

- assess the risks of working on a computer containing malicious software,
- apply the rules to ensure email access, rules against unauthorised use of the community and computer,
- ensure data and communication against abuse,
- evaluate the reliability of information on the World Wide Web,
- recognise computer crime,
- distinguish illegal content.

Content standard:

- spread of computer viruses and spam,
- safe and ethical behaviour on the Internet,
- hacker activity,
- protection of personal data on the Internet (Inovovaný, 2023)

4 Education system in Hungary

The national curriculum defines what students should be taught. The main target group of this document are teachers and school principals, for whom it provides guidance and a framework for their educational activities (1. melléklet, 2023).

In Hungary, the informatics lesson is called digital culture (Magyar, 2023).

4.1 School Curriculum in Hungary

According to the legislation, schools must prepare their own local curricula, which they must develop based on the national core curriculum. The local curriculum must clearly define which is the underlying core curriculum (Tájékoztató, 2023).

4.2 The emergence of information security in digital culture in the national core curriculum in Hungary

In the topic "Protection against the dangers of the digital world," children are faced with the problem that there is a lot of false and misleading information in the digital space and the dangers of the Internet. It is important for students to learn about defence strategies so that, with their teachers' help and their parents' support, they will be able to identify, block, and report negative influences towards them.

The national core curriculum includes the following four sections for each topic:

- learning results,
- development assignments and knowledge,
- concepts,
- recommended activities.

In Hungary, according to the core curriculum of digital culture, it's discussed in 3rd and 4th grades in elementary schools how to protect our privacy and data against the dangers of the digital world. It's recommended that 6 lessons should be spent on this topic in the mentioned grades. There is a topic, "Protection against the dangers of the digital world", which helps children face the fact that there is a lot of false and misleading information in the digital space, as well as the dangers of the Internet. It's important to form such protective methods and strategies, which prepare children to identify, block and report the negative effects towards them. It could be realised together with their teachers and parents.

Learning results:

- While students are learning, they can use simple procedures to determine the authenticity of information found on the Internet.
- Students will be aware of the concept of personal data and understand its importance.
- They know and use different forms of contact and communication channels in the digital environment.
- Students learn about the advantages and limitations of mobile devices and their ethical aspects.
- They have real experience of using mobile devices for educational purposes.

Development assignments and knowledge:

- personal data and its protection,
- methods of recognising online harassment and providing assistance,
- gaining experience with fake news and manipulated content,
- the ethics and safety of online communication,

- online addiction and its knowledge,
- the importance of protecting personal data,
- benefits and risks of using mobile devices.

Concepts: password, blocking, personal data, internet addiction, fake news, gaming addiction, confidential information, exclusion, report, cyberbullying Recommended activities:

- argumentation about the authenticity of the information,
- giving an example of internet bullying,
- playing a situational game about internet attacks/harassment,
- giving advice on reducing the use of digital devices,
- defining sensitive personal data (Oktatási, 2023).

5 Conclusion

A comparison of IT education between Slovakia and Hungary shows some interesting differences. First, the two countries have different amounts of IT lessons in primary and grammar schools. In Slovakia, a total of 9 IT lessons are available for students during the primary and grammar school years, while in Hungary, this number is 11.

In addition, it is important to mention the curriculum differences between the two countries, especially regarding safety and risk. In Slovakia, more emphasis is placed on teaching this, as this topic is mentioned four times in the core curriculum, while in Hungary, it is mentioned only once. So, the conclusion is that more attention is paid to information security education in Slovakia.

Resources

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